

Mean biomasses of *Gloeotrichia* sp. and submerged weeds in plots with and without rice. IRRI, 1979 dry season.

Biotype	Mean biomass (t/ha fresh wt)		Significance of difference
	With rice (15 plots)	Without rice (9 plots)	
Submerged weeds	2.9	7.5	0.01
<i>Gloeotrichia</i>	4.4	1.1	0.06

Possible interactions between rice, weeds, and algae.

correlation remained significant even for the 24-hour measurements, showing that *Gloeotrichia* floating masses were the principal nitrogen-fixing agents involved.

Although the unplanted plots had little floating algae, they had relatively high ARA. That was primarily because *Gloeotrichia* colonies epiphytic on *Chara*

were relatively abundant in the plots. Closer observation showed that *Gloeotrichia* epiphytism was predominant on *Chara* and rare on *Najas*.

The weights of floating *Gloeotrichia* biomasses ranged from 0 to 14 t/ha (mean, 3.3 t/ha). The distribution was log-normal (L-shaped histogram and a mean close to the square root of the variance).

The fresh weights of submerged weed biomasses ranged from 0.2 to 11.8 t/ha (mean, 4.8 t/ha).

The presence of rice increases *Gloeotrichia* growth and decreases the growth of submerged weeds (see table).

Possible relationships between weeds and floating algae were tested by studying correlations between weed and *Gloeotrichia* biomasses and between weed biomasses and 1-hour ARA. Both correlations were significant and negative; the respective *r* values were 0.60 and 0.73 ($r_{0.05} = 0.67$).

Although the results do not fully explain the relationships among the three biotypes, the figure shows some possible interactions.

The results confirm the observation that rice positively affects *Gloeotrichia* growth, either directly by protecting algae against high light intensity, which inhibits their growth or indirectly by limiting the growth of submerged weeds, which seem to compete with floating *Gloeotrichia*. ■

Soil fertility trials in farmers' fields in Sierra Leone

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Soil is tested to provide farmers information that enables them to apply adequate – but not excessive – fertilizer to supplement available nutrients. The All Sierra Leone Coordinated Agronomic Trials conducted in farmers' fields in 1978 provided much data on soil fertility evaluation. The multilocal trials sought to determine if soil testing could help predict rice response to added fertilizer. We defined the “critical level” of a nutrient in a soil as the level below

Table 1. Critical levels of organic carbon, available phosphorus, and exchangeable potassium for dryland rice in Sierra Leone.

Nutrient	Critical level	Rice response (kg/ha)	
		Above critical level	Below critical level
Organic carbon	2.4 (%)	540	590
Av phosphorus	10.0 (ppm)	180	410
Exchangeable potassium	0.07 (meq/100 g)	255	605

Table 2. Critical levels of organic carbon, available phosphorus, and exchangeable potassium for rice in inland valley swamps in Sierra Leone.

Nutrient	Critical level	Rice response (kg/ha)	
		Above critical level	Below critical level
Organic carbon	3.6(%)	600	655
Av phosphorus	5.8 (ppm)	690	875
Exchangeable potassium	0.05 (meq/100 g)	255	520

which the probability of a good response to added fertilizer is high, and above which the probability is low.

The critical level of a particular nutrient is determined as follows:

$$\text{Yield (\%)} = \frac{\text{Yield without nutrient}}{\text{Yield with applied nutrient}} \times 100.$$

The method consists of superimposing

two intersecting lines on the soil test percent yield scatter diagram – one line parallel to the y -axis and the other to the x -axis, drawn in a manner that places the maximum number of points in the lower left and upper right quadrants. The point where the line drawn parallel to the y -axis cuts the x -axis is termed the critical level.

This approach was used with data from the field trials to establish critical

levels for organic carbon, available phosphorus, and exchangeable potassium in Sierra Leone's two dominant rice ecologies: uplands (41 trials) and inland valley swamps (19 trials).

Tables 1 and 2 indicate that fields with less than 2.4% organic carbon, 10 ppm phosphorus, and 0.07 meq exchangeable potassium/100 g soil should respond positively to the corresponding plant nutrients. ■

Nitrogen management in coarse-textured lowland rice soils

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Field studies on nitrogen efficiency have been in progress at this center under the International Network for Soil Fertility

and Fertilizer Evaluation in Rice (INSFFER) Program for the last two seasons. Under the program various nitrogen sources and application methods to rice have been tested on a red sandy loam soil (Alfisol) of intermediate fertility.

Among the several treatments listed, subsoil application of urea gave the best performance at both low and high nitrogen levels (see table). Mudball or supergranule application resulted in

equivalent grain yields. The response to sulfur-coated urea (SCU) was equally encouraging.

Nitrogen efficiency was highest with mudball application. Supergranule and SCU application gave comparable N efficiency. ■

Effects of sources of nitrogen and methods of application on rice yields and nitrogen efficiency, Mandya, Karnataka, 1977 and 1978 kharif.

Source	Method	Grain yield ^a (t/ha)			
		1977 kharif		1978 kharif	
		Low N, 28 kg N/ha	High N, 56 kg N/ha	Low N, 27 kg N/ha	High N, 54 kg N/ha
Control	No nitrogen	2.42 (00)	—	3.50 (00)	—
Urea	Best split (50%, 25%, and 25% N, at planting, tillering, and PI stage)	2.78 (13)	3.21 (14)	4.72 (45)	4.60 (20)
Urea	Basal – band placement in every other row	2.88 (17)	2.84 (8)	—	—
Urea	Basal – mudball for every pair of rows, 10–12 cm soil depth	4.16 (62)	4.83 (43)	—	—
Urea	Basal – supergranules for every pair of rows, 10–12 cm soil depth	3.79 (49)	4.65 (40)	5.12 (60)	5.87 (44)
Urea	Basal – plow sole application	—	—	5.15 (61)	5.72 (41)
SCU	Basal – broadcasting and incorporation	3.74 (47)	4.25 (33)	4.36 (32)	5.44 (36)
SCU	Basal – plow sole application	—	—	4.87 (51)	5.94 (45)
SCU	Basal – broadcasting and incorporation	—	—	4.45 (35)	5.39 (35)

^aFigures in parentheses indicate the nitrogen efficiency in kilogram grain/kilogram of applied N. Kharif = wet season. PI = panicle initiation.

	IR20	Rasi
General mean yield (t/ha)	3.55	5.03
CD at 0.05	0.63	0.64
CV (%)	12.70	10.00

Effect of azolla inoculation on rice yields

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The water fern azolla, in association with the blue-green algae *Anabaena azollae*, can fix atmospheric nitrogen and supply it to the rice crop after decomposition. The effects of azolla incorporation on rice yield were studied. A field experiment using IR20 was conducted in a randomized block design with four replications in the 1978–79navarai season. Treatments were:

- 0-50-50 kg NPK/ha
- 25-50-50 kg NPK/ha
- 50-50-50 kg NPK/ha
- 75-50-50 kg NPK/ha
- 100-50-50 kg NPK/ha
- 0-50-50 kg NPK/ha + azolla
- 25-50-50 kg NPK/ha + azolla
- 50-50-50 kg NPK/ha + azolla
- 75-50-50 kg NPK/ha + azolla
- 100-50-50 kg NPK/ha + azolla

Urea, superphosphate and muriate of potash were used as sources of N, P, and K. Seven days after transplanting, 300 g azolla/m² was inoculated. In about 2 weeks azolla covered the plot surface and was incorporated.

Azolla incorporation increased yields